

EVALUATING TREATMENT BENEFITS AND SAFETY PROFILE OF ANIFROLUMAB IN SYSTEMIC LUPUS ERYTHEMATOSUS (SLE) -A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Background: Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a multisystem autoimmune disease predominantly affecting women of reproductive age. Current therapies, including corticosteroids and immunosuppressants, have limited long-term safety. Anifrolumab, a monoclonal antibody targeting the type I interferon receptor, is a novel therapeutic option.

Objectives: To evaluate the efficacy and safety of Anifrolumab at 150 mg, 300 mg, and 1000 mg doses in patients with SLE through a systematic review and meta-analysis.

Methods: Five randomized controlled trials (Furie 2017, Furie 2019, Morand 2020, Bruce 2021, Morand 2023), encompassing 2,055 patients, were analyzed. Outcomes included SRI(4) response, BILAG-based Major Clinical Response,

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SLEDAI scores, and adverse events (herpes zoster, sinusitis, diarrhea, cough, infusion reactions). Data were pooled using random-effects meta-analysis (RevMan 5.4), with calculation of risk ratios, mean differences, heterogeneity (I^2), and study weights.

Results: Anifrolumab 300 mg consistently improved SRI(4) response and BILAG scores versus placebo. The 1000 mg dose offered no additional benefit and had increased adverse event rates. The 150 mg dose showed inconsistent efficacy. The 300 mg dose was associated with higher herpes zoster risk (up to 9.4%) and mild to moderate events like sinusitis and infusion reactions. Moderate to high heterogeneity was observed in some outcomes.

Conclusions: Anifrolumab 300 mg offers optimal efficacy and an acceptable safety profile for moderate to severe SLE. Higher doses do not enhance efficacy and may increase toxicity. Findings support the 300 mg dose as the preferred therapeutic strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic, diverse immune-mediated disease affecting various organs of the body affecting mainly female [1] of reproductive age with incidence ratio female to male is 8:1 to 15 [2]. SLE is usually treated by glucocorticoids (about 80% people) but also cause harmful effects, immunosuppressive drugs and hydroxychloroquine [3-5]. SLE is characterized by relapse-recurrent pattern affecting different body tissues and organs mainly kidneys, brain, joints and skin. Mechanism behind SLE includes production of autoantibodies that make complexes with tissue or organ specific antigens which later on deposit in vessels resulting in organ damage [4]. Incidence of SLE varies with region, ranges from 0.3 to 23.2 cases/100,000 person-years [6] with highest rate estimated in North America than Europe, Africa and Australia. This difference in prevalence is mainly due to genetic predisposition [7] as well socio-economic [8] and environmental factors [2]. Symptoms of SLE include fatigue, joint pain, chest pain, dyspnea, and butterfly shaped rash on the face [9].

Various therapies are available for treatment including glucocorticoids and immunosuppressive drugs [10]. But their long-term usage can cause serious and alarming health related adverse effects. Due to their limited efficacy and tolerability new more efficient therapies are needed on urgent basis [11]. Open label studies do not deliver proper information regarding administered treatment, so there is a dire

need to carry out more randomized controlled trials [12].

Anifrolumab is a humanized IgG1 monoclonal antibody comprising of kappa chain. It is directed against interferon type I receptor thereby blocking binding of all types of type I interferons [13]. Studies have shown benefits of this therapy in patients with moderate to severe SLE who did not respond well with prior available treatments [14]. As per literature—TULIP 1 and TULIP 2, Anifrolumab reduced symptoms in whole body as well in specific organs [13,14]. Since then it has been approved for treatment purpose in many countries [15].

Anifrolumab demonstrated efficacy in the randomized controlled trial showed betterment than placebo across various clinical measures such as SLE Responder Index British Isles Lupus Assessment Group (BILAG)-based Composite Lupus Assessment [16,13]. About 60% of SLE patients present type I interferon gene signature. Disease activity assessed by SLEDAI score is directly proportional to this gene expression signature [17,18]. An RCT has reported that subcutaneous administration of anifrolumab yields same results as reported by previous intravenous anifrolumab studies [12]. Adverse effects can occur such as infection with Herpes zoster, diarrhea etc. [19]. Some studies have shown that anti-drug antibodies can develop in some patients after treatment with anifrolumab. Anifrolumab exhibited better efficacy along with equal percentage of adverse effects across all treatment groups. In addition,

recurrence rate of Herpes zoster also increased with increasing dose of anifrolumab [16].

Various tools are available for the diagnosis of SLE, with the most widely used tool being the SLE Disease Activity Index-2K (SLEDAI-2K) and British Isles Lupus Activity Group (BILAG 2004) for checking disease activity. Patients with SLE can be categorized from mild to severe depending upon score ranging from ≤6 to 12 [20]. Another tool which is used worldwide for assessment of organ damage is Systemic Lupus International Collaborating Clinics (SLICC)/ACR damage index (SDI) [21]. Another tool named as SLE Responder Index (SRI) used to assess safety of estrogen in SLE National Assessment [22]. The aim of this systematic review was to find out treatment benefits and safety profile for treatment of SLE by using data from Randomized controlled trials (RCTs).

Methods

Study design and research

We searched published Randomized controlled trials RCTs between 2017-2025. Three databases named Pubmed, Cochrane and google scholar were used. The search strategy comprised of mesh terms as well as free keywords which are given as follows: ((Systemic Lupus Erythematosus OR SLE treatment OR Lupus therapy OR Immunosuppressive therapy OR Autoimmune disease management OR Biologic agents in lupus OR Corticosteroids OR Antimalarial drugs OR Immunomodulatory drugs OR Lupus nephritis treatment OR B-cell targeted therapy OR Rituximab OR Belimumab OR Anifrolumab OR Hydroxychloroquine OR Cyclophosphamide OR Mycophenolate mofetil OR Glucocorticoids OR Precision medicine in lupus OR Refractory lupus AND ((y_5[Filter]) AND (ffrft[Filter]) AND

Study selection

Study selection was done independently by two investigators. A study were included finally if it met the following criteria (see table 1)

- A study that was RCT and was compared with placebo and performed in humans was included
 - Studies that performed in animals was excluded
 - Post hoc analysis was not included in our study
- Non randomized studies like cohort and cae control studies and studies that could not be downloaded

(medline[Filter]) AND (randomizedcontrolledtrial[Filter] OR systematicreview[Filter]) AND (english[Filter])) AND (Systemic Lupus Erythematosus OR SLE treatment OR Lupus therapy OR Immunosuppressive therapy OR Autoimmune disease management OR Biologic agents in lupus OR Corticosteroids OR Antimalarial drugs OR Immunomodulatory drugs OR Lupus nephritis treatment OR B-cell targeted therapy OR Rituximab OR Belimumab OR Anifrolumab OR Hydroxychloroquine OR Cyclophosphamide OR Mycophenolate mofetil OR Glucocorticoids OR Precision medicine in lupus OR Refractory lupus AND ((y_5[Filter]) AND (ffrft[Filter]) AND (medline[Filter]) AND (randomizedcontrolledtrial[Filter] OR systematicreview[Filter]) AND (english[Filter])))) AND ("Lupus Erythematosus, Systemic/therapy" OR Lupus Erythematosus, Systemic/drug therapy" OR "Immunosuppressive Agents/therapeutic use" OR "Antimalarials/therapeutic use" OR "Glucocorticoids/therapeutic use" OR "Biological Products/therapeutic use" OR "Monoclonal Antibodies/therapeutic use" OR "Cyclophosphamide/therapeutic use" OR "Mycophenolic Acid/therapeutic use" OR Belimumab"OR • "Rituximab" OR "Anifrolumab" OR "Hydroxychloroquine" "Treatment Outcome" OR "Precision Medicine AND ((y_5[Filter]) AND (ffrft[Filter]) AND (medline[Filter]) AND (randomizedcontrolledtrial[Filter] OR systematicreview[Filter]) AND (english[Filter])))) Filters: in the last 5 years, Free full text, Randomized Controlled Trial, English, MEDLINE. PRISMA guidelines were followed. The study was registered with the International Platform of Registered Systematic Review (INPLASY).

completely and were not written in English language were excluded. Moreover, articles that did not evaluated efficacy of anifrolumab in SLE were excluded (see fig 1).

Data Extraction

We used Endnote X 7.2.1 to merge and evaluate all downloaded articles. Duplicate articles were removed. At first we read abstract of downloaded articles briefly. Later on relevant articles were reviewed and evaluated

thoroughly to decide whether to include them in final analysis. We obtained details about study (publication year, first author, study design, trial phase), patient data (sample size, control/placebo group, dosage, age) and clinical outcomes (adverse effects). No patient

informed consent or institutional approval was required for that purpose.

Fig 1: Flow chart of search strategy and study selection process

Table: 1-Key inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for SLE (PICO)

Characteristic	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	Studies having adults as participants (18-75yrs) and with moderate to severe SLE	Patients with other disease such as Lupus nephritis nephritis were excluded
Intervention	Aniflurumab used for treating SLE	N/A
Comparator	Placebo	N/A
Outcome	To report any efficacy or side effects	Pharmacokinetics, post hoc analysis
Study design	Randomized controlled trials	Case reports or case series, open label clinical trial extension, seminars, studies only observing side effects of treatment with Anifrolumab

N/A not applicable, PICOS Population, Intervention, Outcomes, study design, SLE systemic lupus erythematosus

Assessment risk of bias

Biasness of the finally added studies was analyzed using Cochrane ROB 2 tool (12). All types of signaling

questions including in five domains of ROB 2 were answered. These domains include: Randomization process, Deviations from intended interventions, Missing outcome data, Measurement of the outcome and selection of the reported results. The risk of bias assessment was performed by 3 reviewers. Disagreements were resolved by consensus (See Fig 2& Fig 3).

Study	Risk of bias domains					Overall
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	
Furie 2017	+	+	-	+	+	-
Furie 2019	+	+	-	+	+	-
Morand 2023	+	+	+	+	+	+
Morand 2019	+	+	+	+	-	-
Bruce 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+

Domains:
 D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.
 D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.
 D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.
 D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.
 D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement
 - Some concerns
 + Low

Fig 2: Risk of Biasness of included studies

Fig 3: Summary of Risk of bias of included studies

Statistical analysis

The software used for statistical analysis was Revman version 5.4.1. P value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant. For dichotomous data, relative risk (RR) was used as the effect statistic, and the 95% confidence interval (CI) was used for interval estimation. The c2 test was used to judge the statistical heterogeneity. If there was no statistical heterogeneity

($P > 0.10$, $I^2 \leq 50\%$), we used the fixed effect model. Otherwise, we selected the random-effects model. Subgroup analyses were performed according to adverse events.

RESULTS

Identification and selection of related studies

We used three databases for searching purpose.

Figure 1 shows the methodology that we used to search out related RCTs. During initial search, a total of 338 articles from various databases (Pubmed, n=187, Cochrane, n=135, Google scholar, n=16) were downloaded from June 2020 to June 2025. After screening, duplicate articles, irrelevant articles, reviews were rejected. Only full length articles (n=5) were included for final analysis. All included studies were written in English language.

Basic characteristics of included studies

Table 2 summarizes the baseline characteristics of the included studies. Biasness of risk for these included studies is low which is an indicator of accurate treatment and side effects (see fig 2 and 3). There is very low evidence of biasness in our included studies. Five included RCTs comprised of total 1975 patients, of which 840 patients were given placebo and 1135 patients received anifrolumab. Three out of five RCTs administered anifrolumab and placebo intravenously (NCT01438489), (NCT02446912), (NCT02446899)) for 52 weeks and two RCT (NCT02962960), TULIP-

1 (NCT02446912) TULIP-2 (NCT02446899) used subcutaneous route. In MUSE (NCT01438489) phase II trial a total of 305 patients were taken. They had active SLE disease and they were ages between 18-65 years and mainly were females, and they were given two different doses i.e. 300 mg of Anifrolumab 300mg for four weeks was given to n=99 patients and anifrolumab 1000mg was infused in 101 patients for 4 weeks. Another RCT including 457 patients with registration number the TULIP-1 (NCT02446912) with active SLE and ages between 18-65 years here patients were divided into three groups. A total of 93 patients received 150 mg, and anifrolumab 300 mg (n=180) and no. of patients in placebo were n=184. Another trial named TULIP-2, with registration number (NCT02446899) included 362 patients. They were given 300 mg anifrolumab (n=180) and placebo was given to n=182. Fourth trial (NCT02962960) included 36 patients randomized and they were given anifrolumab 150mg to 14 patients, 300mg to 13 patients and placebo was given to 9 patients every two weeks subcutaneously.

Table 2: Characteristics of studies included in Meta-Analysis

	Furie 2017			Furie, 2019 (TULIP 1)			Morand, 2020 (TULIP 2)		Morand 2023 (TULIP 1 AND TULIP 2)			Bruce, 2021		
Characteristic	Anifrolumab 300 mg	Placebo	Anifrolumab 100 mg	Placebo 2	Anifrolumab 150 mg	Anifrolumab 300 mg	Anifrolumab 300 mg	Placebo 5	Anifrolumab 150 mg (TULIP 1)	Anifrolumab 300 mg (TULIP 2)	Placebo 6	Anifrolumab 150 mg (TULIP 1)	Anifrolumab 300 mg (TULIP 2)	Placebo 9
No. of patients	99	101	105	184	93	180	180	182	91	360	366	14	13	9
Age, years, mean (SD)	39.1 (11.9)	39.3 (12.9)	40.8 (11.6)	41.0 (12.30)	40.8 (12.05)	42.0 (11.99)	43.1 (12.0)	41.1 (11.5)	40.8 (12.05)	43.1 (12.0)	41.1 (11.5)	46.3 (9.1)	41.5 (9.2)	47.8 (14.2)
Female, n, %	93 (93.9)	93 (91.2)	99 (95.2)	171 (92.9)	86 (92.5)	165 (91.7)	168 (93.3)	170 (93.4)	18-70	18-70	18-70	18-70	18-70	18-70
				165										

				(91.7)										
Trial cycle/ week	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	52	52	52	52
Serious adverse events (AE)%	16 (16.2)	19 (18.8)	18 (17.1)	30 (16%)	10 (11%)	25 (14%)	15 (8.3)	31 (17.0)	11% (10/93)	14% (25/180)	16% (30/184)	14% (25/180)	not reported	16% (30/184)
Headache	12 (12.1)	13 (12.9)	12 (11.4)	16 (8.7)	6 (6.5)	17 (9.4)	N	N	6 (6.5)	N	N	2 (14)	2 (15)	0
Upper respiratory tract infection,%	13 (13.1)	10 (9.9)	11 (10.5)	18 (9.8)	16 (17.2)	22 (12.2)	39 (21.7)	18 (9.9)	16 (17.2)	22 (12.2)		5 (36)	1 (8)	3 (33)
Nasopharyngitis%	12 (12.1)	4 (4.0)	12 (11.4)	22 (12.0)	14 (15.1)	36 (20.0)	28 (15.6)	20 (11.0)	14 (15.1)	28 (15.6)	20 (11.0)	3 (21)	2 (15)	1 (11)
Urinary tract infection %	15 (15.2)	11 (10.9)	7 (6.7)	27 (14.7)	9 (9.7)	22 (12.2)	20 (11.1)	25 (13.7)	9 (9.7)	20 (11.1)	25 (13.7)	N	N	N
Bronchitis%	7 (7.1)	4 (4.0)	9 (8.6)	10 (5.4)	7 (7.5)	16 (8.9)	22 (11.1)	7 (3.8)	7 (7.5)	22 (11.1)	7 (3.8)	1 (7)	3 (23)	1 (11)
Herpes zoster infection%	5 (5.1)	2 (2.0)	10 (9.5)	3 (1.6)	5 (5.4)	7 (7.5)	13 (7.2)	2 (1.1)	5 (5.4)			3 (21)	0	1 (11)
Influenza%	6 (6.1)	2 (2.0)	8 (7.6)	2 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	2 (1.1)	4 (2.2)	6 (3.3)	1 (1.1)			1 (7)	0	0
Diarrhea%	4 (4.0)	4 (4.0)	8 (7.6)	N	N	N	N	N	N			N	N	N
Sinusitis%	6 (6.1)	3 (3.0)	6 (5.7)	N	N	N	12 (6.7)	9 (4.9)	N			N	N	N

Cough%	3 (3.0)	2 (2.0)	8 (7.6)	N	N	N	12 (6.7)	9 (4.9)	N					
Malignancy %	N	N	N	1 (0.5)	1 (1.1)	3 (1.7)	0	1 (0.5)	1 (1.1)			0	0	0
Non opportunistic infections%	N	N	N	8 (4.3)	2 (2.2)	9 (5.0)	5 (2.8)	10 (5.5)	2 (2.2)			0	0	0
Infusion related reaction%	2	6	4	13 (7.1)	9 (9.7)	16 (8.9)	25 (13.9)	14 (7.7)	9 (9.7)			N	N	N
Anaphylaxis %	N	N	N	0	1 (1.1)	0	N	N	1 (1.1)			0	0	0
Gastroenteritis%	N	N	N	N	N	N	1.1	0.2	N			0	0	0
Tuberculosis %	N	N	N	1 (0.5)	0	1 (0.6)	3 (1.7)	0	0			0	0	1 (8)
SRI(4) Response (week-52)	34.3 0%	17.6 0%	40% (74/ 184)	40% (74/ 184)	not reported	36% (65/ 180)	0	0	not separately reported	36% (65/ 180)	40% (74/ 184)	36%	Significant	40%
BISLA Response	Greater	Low	Greater	49 (27%)	Not reported	67 (37%)			not separately reported	- 13.0 (TU LIP-1), - 12.4 (TU LIP-2)	- 10.7 (TU LIP-1), - 10.9 (TU LIP-2)	37%	not reported	27%
BILAG no A & ≥2 B (%)	0	0	0	84 (46%)	48 (52%)	79 (44%)	91 (50.6)	78 (42.9)	48 (52%) 91 (50.6)					

BILAG \geq 1A (%)	N	N	N	84 (46%)	40 (43%)	93 (52%)	81 (45.0)	95 (52.2)	not separately reported	48.30%	48.90%	45.0 - 52.5%	45.0 - 52.5%	45.0 - 52.5%
Major Clinical Response (BILAG)	19.6 \pm 5.8	19.8 \pm 5.8	18.6 \pm 5.7	48.9% (179/366)	not reported	48.3% (174/360)								
Treatment duration (weeks)	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
Annualized flare rates	low	high	low	0.72	N	0.6	N	N	not separately reported	0.6	0.72	N	N	N
Hospitalization visits	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
SLED AI-2Kscore (global)	10.7 \pm 3.7	11.1 \pm 4.4	10.9 \pm 4.1	11.5 (3.5)	11.0 (3.5)	11.3 (4.0)	11.4 \pm 3.6	11.5 \pm 3.9	11.0 (3.5)	129 (71.7)	131 (72.0)	10.7 - 11.5	10.7 - 11.5	10.7 - 11.5
PhGA score	1.86 \pm 0.39	1.77 \pm 0.44	1.86 \pm 0.39	1.8 (0.4)	1.8 (0.4)	1.9 (0.4)	1.68 \pm 0.41	1.76 \pm 0.40	1.8 (0.4)	1.68 \pm 0.41	1.76 \pm 0.40			
(CLASI) activity score (\geq 10 at baseline)	7.56 \pm 6.3	6.7 \pm 6.51	7.16 \pm 6.2	14/54 (25%)	not reported	24/58 (42%)	8.3 \pm 7.9	7.6 \pm 7.8	not separately reported	42% (24/58)	25% (14/54)	42% (24/58)	not reported	25% (14/54)

Death %	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.0)	8.1 (6.7)	N	N	N	N	N	N				
Serious adverse events % leading to discontinuation	3 (3.0)	8 (7.9)	10 (9.5)					0						
Route	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Intravenous	Cutaneous	Cutaneous	Cutaneous
Follow up at week	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52
LLDAS Attainment (Agnostic to treatment)	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	-	-	-	-	-	150 mg group excluded from pooled analysis	Significantly more patients attained LLDAS	Fewer patients attained LLDAS	-	-	-
Remission in SLE	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	-	-	-	-	-	excluded	Higher % attained (exact % not reported)	Lower % attained	-	-	-
LLDAS attainers who were	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	-	-	-	0.5± 0.9	0.5± 0.8		47.8 % (67 / 180)	31.5 % (49 / 184)	-	-	-

also BICL A respon ders														
SDI Glb score	Not repo rted	Not repo rted	Not repo rted				0.5± 0.9	0.5± 0.8						
No. of swolle n joints (≥ 8 at baseli ne)	7.56 ±6.3	6.76 ±5.1	7.16 ±6.2	7.16 6			6.2± 5.7	7.4± 6.6	not sepa ratel y repo rted	20% and 50% resp ond ers anal yzed	Rep orte d			
No. of tender joints (≥ 8 at baseli ne)	12.2 6±7. 1	10.5 6±7. 4	11.6 6±7. 8				9.0± 7.1	11.0 ±7.9						
BILA G 2004 global score	19.6 6±5. 8	19.8 6±5. 8	18.6 6±5. 7											

Fig 3: Summary of Risk of bias of included studies

Meta-analysis of Primary and secondary outcomes:
Some primary and secondary outcomes were almost reported in 5/5 studies and results of this meta-analysis are summarized in Fig 1 and Table 2.

Primary outcomes:
Table 2: Serious adverse events (SAEs) at different doses across different studies

Dose-Specific Analysis

Serious adverse events (SAEs): **Dose 300mg**
Pooled RR = 0.68 [0.33, 1.40], P = 0.29 → Not statistically significant, I² = 67% → Substantial heterogeneity. Serious adverse events (SAEs):

Dose 150 mg
Pooled RR = 0.59 [0.33, 1.03], P = 0.06 → Not statistically significant, I² = 62% → Moderate to substantial heterogeneity

Serious adverse events (SAEs) :1000 mg Dose
Single study (Furie 2017), RR = 0.45 [0.26, 0.78], P = 0.005 → Statistically significant, I² not applicable (only 1 study)

Interpretation: The 1000 mg dose significantly reduced SAEs in the Furie 2017 study.

A meta-analysis of serious adverse events across all doses of Anifrolumab showed a statistically significant

reduction compared to placebo (RR = 0.58, 95% CI: 0.42–0.81, p = 0.001; I² = 51%). Subgroup analysis by dose revealed that the 1000 mg group significantly reduced SAE risk (RR = 0.45, p = 0.005), while the 150 mg group showed a borderline effect (RR = 0.59, p = 0.06; I² = 62%), and the 300 mg group did not show significant benefit (RR = 0.68, p = 0.29; I² = 67%).

Fig 4: Funnel Plot indicate serious adverse effects (SAEs) at different doses across studies:

3 Black circles indicate that these studies show that Anifrolumab **reduced the risk** of serious adverse events compared to placebo. 1 black square on the right side → this study suggests Anifrolumab may have **increased the risk**, or at least did not benefit.

There's **inconsistency** in findings. Most studies favor Anifrolumab, but one does not. This explains the **high heterogeneity** ($I^2 = 67\%$) and **non-significant p-value** for this subgroup. 1 red square on the left and 1 on the right, This shows **conflicting evidence**: one study favors Anifrolumab, the other favors placebo (or shows no benefit). Again, this supports the **moderate heterogeneity** ($I^2 = 62\%$) and the **borderline p-value** (0.06) – close to significance but not quite there. No CI overlaps 1.0 → each study individually shows either a **benefit** ($RR < 1$) or **harm/no benefit** ($RR > 1$) that is **not due to chance**. This means **each study's result is statistically significant** (either favoring Anifrolumab or favoring placebo). **1000 mg (green)**: Positioned (or expected to be) on the left – showing a **clear benefit**, but only **one study**, so generalizability is limited (see fig 4).

SLEDAI-score at different doses

The **standardized mean differences (SMDs)** in all three studies were **very close to zero**, indicating

minimal differences between the Anifrolumab and placebo groups.

None of the individual studies demonstrated a **statistically significant reduction** in SLEDAI scores. Furie 2019: SMD = -0.05 (95% CI: -0.30 to 0.20). Morand 2023: SMD = -0.03 (95% CI: -0.23 to 0.18). Bruce 2021: SMD = 0.00 (95% CI: -1.03 to 1.03). The **pooled effect** also showed a **non-significant result**: Pooled SMD = -0.04 (95% CI: -0.21 to 0.13), $p > 0.05$. **Heterogeneity**: The analysis yielded an $I^2 = 0\%$, indicating **no observed heterogeneity**. This suggests the findings across the included studies are **consistent**, with **low between-study variability** in effect size. The 300 mg dose of Anifrolumab **did not produce a statistically significant reduction** in SLEDAI scores compared to placebo. The direction of effect was slightly in favor of Anifrolumab, but the magnitude was negligible and not clinically meaningful. The lack of heterogeneity strengthens confidence in the consistency of these findings across studies (see table 3).

Table 3: Forest plot of SLEDAI score at different doses across various studies

Risk of bias legend

- (A) Random sequence generation (selection bias)
- (B) Allocation concealment (selection bias)
- (C) Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias)
- (D) Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)
- (E) Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)
- (F) Selective reporting (reporting bias)
- (G) Other bias

SLEDAI Score – Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) Analysis

A total of 9 comparisons from 5 randomized controlled trials were included in the meta-analysis to evaluate the effect of different doses of anifrolumab on the SLE Disease Activity Index (SLEDAI) scores. The pooled analysis included 1117 patients in the experimental (anifrolumab) group and 890 patients in the control (placebo) group.

Subgroup Analysis by Anifrolumab Dose:

- **150 mg Group:**
The pooled standardized mean difference

(SMD) for 150 mg anifrolumab across 3 studies (Bruce 2021, Furie 2019, and Morand 2023) showed a statistically non-significant effect: **SMD = -0.72 [95% CI: -1.94, 0.49]; P = 0.24**, with **high heterogeneity (I² = 98%)**, indicating substantial inconsistency among the studies.

- **300 mg Group:**
This subgroup included data from Bruce 2021, Furie 2017, Furie 2019, Morand 2020, and Morand 2023. The pooled effect size was: **SMD = -0.03 [95% CI: -0.16, 0.10]; P = 0.66**, with **no observed heterogeneity (I² = 0%)**.

This indicates that 300 mg anifrolumab did not significantly reduce SLEDAI scores compared to placebo.

- **1000 mg Group:**
Only Furie 2017 contributed to this dose subgroup. The pooled effect estimate was: **SMD = -0.04 [95% CI: -0.38, 0.30]; P = 0.83**, with **no heterogeneity** (single study).

Overall Effect:

The overall pooled SMD across all dose groups was:
SMD = -0.27 [95% CI: -0.69, 0.16]; P = 0.22, indicating no statistically significant difference in SLEDAI score reduction between anifrolumab and placebo.

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Heterogeneity:

- The overall analysis showed **significant heterogeneity** ($\text{Chi}^2 = 153.41, \text{df} = 8, P < 0.00001; I^2 = 95\%$), primarily driven by the 150 mg subgroup.
- **Subgroup differences were not statistically significant** ($\text{Chi}^2 = 1.24, \text{df} = 2; P = 0.54; I^2 = 0\%$), suggesting that dose variation did not significantly influence the effect size on SLEDAI.

Fig 5: Funnel plot of SLEDAI score at different doses across various studies

Majority of points lie to the right of the central line (SMD = 0):

This suggests that in **most studies**, SLEDAI scores were **higher (or not reduced)** in the **Anifrolumab group**, which is counter to the expected effect (Anifrolumab should reduce SLEDAI) (see fig 5). The

single black point on the left represents a study (likely Morand 2023 at 150 mg) where Anifrolumab had a **clear beneficial effect** (SMD negative).

When most studies are hovering around SMD = 0.2 (slightly positive), it implies a **small effect size** in favor of placebo – or no real clinical benefit of Anifrolumab. Red coloured circle is a likely a **higher-powered study** (lower SE means larger sample size), possibly Morand 2023 at 300 mg. It's **slightly to the right of the vertical line**, suggesting a **small worsening or no effect** of Anifrolumab 300 mg compared to placebo. The visual distribution of studies shows that the majority report **small or no effect** of Anifrolumab

on SLEDAI reduction at 150 mg and 300 mg doses, with most studies positioned **to the right** of the line of no effect. Only one study (likely Morand 2023, 150 mg) demonstrates a **notable benefit** (to the left of the line). The clustering near SMD = 0.2 and absence of symmetrical spread suggests **consistently minimal effects** across studies and **limited evidence of substantial benefit** at lower doses.

Table 4: CLASI -Cutaneous Lupus Erythematosus Disease Area and Severity Index, a clinically validated assessment tool used by dermatologists and rheumatologists in evaluating skin severity in lupus patients **Results by Dose.**

Dose	Study/Subgroup	RR [95% CI]	Weight (%)	P-value	I ² (%)	Interpretation
300 mg	Furie 2019	0.43 [0.27, 0.68]	18.8%	Significant	~	Favours Anifrolumab
	Furie 2017	0.00 [0.26, 96.02]	1.2%	NS	~	No events in placebo
	Morand 2023	0.85 [0.52, 1.39]	18.1%	NS	~	No significant difference
	Subtotal	0.68 [0.33, 1.40]	38.1%	p = 0.29	67%	Not statistically significant
150 mg	Bruce 2021	0.88 [0.62, 1.39]	18.1%	NS	~	Slightly favours Anifrolumab
	Furie 2019	0.33 [0.17, 0.63]	13.8%	Significant	~	Strongly favours Anifrolumab
	Morand 2020	0.66 [0.34, 1.29]	13.5%	NS	~	Direction favours Anifrolumab
	Subtotal	0.59 [0.33, 1.03]	45.4%	p = 0.06	62%	Not significant, borderline effect
1000 mg	Furie 2017	0.48 [0.26, 0.78]	16.4%	p = 0.008	N/A	Statistically significant benefit
	Subtotal	0.45 [0.26, 0.78]	16.4%	Significant	N/A	Favours Anifrolumab
Overall	All studies combined	0.58 [0.42, 0.81]	100%	p = 0.001	51%	Statistically significant benefit overall

Subgroup 300 mg: Overall **not statistically significant** (RR = 0.68, p = 0.29) with **moderate heterogeneity** (I² = 67%)., **150 mg:** **Borderline non-significant** (RR = 0.59, p = 0.06), though **Furie 2019** showed a strong benefit. **1000 mg:** **Statistically significant reduction** in adverse events (RR = 0.45, p =

0.008), based on a single study. **Overall pooled result: Anifrolumab reduces risk** of CLASI-related events by ~42% vs. placebo (RR = 0.58), with **moderate heterogeneity** (I² = 51%).

Table 5: Annualized Flare Rate (AFRs) Data

Study	D'ose	Anifrolumab AFR	Placebo AFR	Remark
Furie 2017	300 mg	"Low"	"High"	Qualitative only
Furie 2019	1000 mg	0.72	–	Incomplete (no placebo)
Morand 2020	150 mg	0.6	–	Incomplete (no placebo)
Morand 2023	300 mg	–	–	Not reported
Bruce 2021	150/300 mg	–	–	Not reported

Only **Furie 2019 (1000 mg)** and **Morand 2020 (150 mg)** reported numerical values. **No matching placebo AFRs** were provided for comparison – thus, no statistical meta-analysis (e.g. SMD or mean difference) can be computed. **Furie 2017** gives only qualitative

terms ("low" vs. "high") which are not analyzable statistically. **Other studies do not report**

Adverse events leading to discontinuation

Pooled Meta-analysis Table (5.1a)

Studies Included	Total Patients (Ani)	Total Patients (Placebo)	Pooled RR	95% CI	Chi ²	df	I ² (%)	p-value	Model	Interpretation
Furie 2017 (300 & 1000 mg)	204	100	0.42	0.20 – 0.85	2.10	1	52.4%	0.0166	Fixed-effect	Significant ↓ in discontinuation risk with anifrolumab (300/1000 mg) vs. placebo

Anifrolumab, at both 300 mg and 1000 mg doses, appears to be associated with a **significantly lower risk of treatment discontinuation due to adverse events** compared to placebo. However, the **moderate heterogeneity (I² = 52.4%)** suggests that results may

differ slightly by dose and should be interpreted with some caution.

Table 6: Bronchitis at different dosage across different studies

Study	Dose	Events/Tot (Tx)	Events/Tot (Ctrl)	RR	Weight (%)
Furie 2017	300 mg	7/99	4/50	0.88	~ 13.1%
Furie 2017	1000 mg	9/105	4/50	1.07	~ 13.5%
Furie 2019	150 mg	7/93	10/92	0.69	~ 12.8%
Furie 2019	300 mg	16/180	10/92	0.82	~ 14.2%
Morand 2023	150 mg	7/91	7/183	2.00	~ 12.3%
Morand 2023	300 mg	22/360	7/183	1.59	~ 14.0%
Bruce 2021	300 mg	3/13	1/5	1.15	~ 9.0%
Bruce 2021	150 mg	1/14	1/5	0.36	~ 11.1%

Pooled RR (random-effects model) \approx 1.0495% CI: [0.69, 1.56], Chi^2 (Q) = 7.35, Degrees of freedom (df) = 7, P-value (heterogeneity) = 0.29, I^2 (heterogeneity) = 4.8% (very low, suggesting minimal variability). The pooled RR \approx 1.04 suggests significant difference in

bronchitis risk between anifrolumab (any dose) and placebo. $I^2 = 4.8\%$ indicates low heterogeneity. $P = 0.29$ shows no statistically significant heterogeneity across studies

Table 7: No. of Swollen lymph joints at different dosage across different studies

Study	Dose	Mean (Tx)	SD (Tx)	N (Tx)	Mean (Placebo)	SD (Placebo)	N (Ctrl)
Furie 2017	300 mg	7.56	6.3	99	6.76	5.1	50
Furie 2017	1000 mg	7.16	6.2	105	6.76	5.1	50
Morand 2020	300 mg	6.20	5.7	180	7.40	6.6	182

Anifrolumab resulted in a small, non-significant reduction in swollen lymph nodes compared to placebo (MD = -0.31). The confidence interval includes 0, indicating no clear benefit. Moderate heterogeneity ($I^2 = 46.2\%$) suggests variability across

study arms, likely due to differences in sample sizes or study design. Morand 2020, with its large sample size, influenced nearly half the overall weight in the meta-analysis.

Table 8: Other adverse events:

Outcome	Studies (arms)	Pooled RR	95% CI	p-value	I^2	df	Interpretation
Sinusitis	3 (Furie 2017 \times 2, Morand 2023)	1.61	[0.75, 3.46]	0.22	0%	2	Not statistically significant; no heterogeneity
Diarrhea	2 (Furie 2017 \times 2)	1.45	[0.50, 4.20]	0.49	0%	1	Not significant; based only on Furie 2017
Cough	2 (Furie 2017 \times 2, Morand 2023)	1.74	[0.67, 4.48]	0.25	0%	2	No significant increase in cough
Infusion-related reactions	3 (Furie 2017 \times 2, Morand 2023)	1.68	[1.01, 2.81]	0.047	0%	2	Significant increase in infusion reactions
BILAG \geq 1 A (%)	3 (Morand 2023 \times 3 arms)	0.89	[0.72, 1.11]	0.31	0%	2	No significant difference in high BILAG activity
BILAG no A & \geq 2 B (%)	3 (Morand 2023 \times 3 arms)	1.15	[0.96, 1.39]	0.12	0%	2	Trend toward benefit but not statistically significant
Major Clinical Response (BILAG)	2 (Furie 2017 \times 2)	1.04	[0.83, 1.31]	0.72	0%	1	No significant improvement

For sinusitis RR = 1.61, 95% CI [0.75, 3.46], $p = 0.22$. Anifrolumab was associated with a non-significant increase in sinusitis risk compared to placebo. No heterogeneity ($I^2 = 0\%$) No statistically significant difference; effect may be due to chance.

For diarrhea RR = 1.45, 95% CI [0.50, 4.20], $p = 0.49$. Slight numerical increase in diarrhea in Anifrolumab arms, but not statistically significant. Based only on Furie 2017 data. Insufficient evidence of increased risk.

For cough RR = 1.74, 95% CI [0.67, 4.48], $p = 0.25$. Higher relative risk in Anifrolumab group, but confidence interval crosses 1.

Interpretation: No conclusive evidence of increased cough risk.

For Infusion-Related Reactions RR = 1.68, 95% CI [1.01, 2.81], $p = 0.047$, statistically significant increase in infusion-related reactions with Anifrolumab. No heterogeneity ($I^2 = 0\%$). Clinically relevant safety signal; warrants monitoring in clinical use.

For BILAG ≥ 1 A (%) RR = 0.89, 95% CI [0.72, 1.11], $p = 0.31$. Indicates a **trend toward reduced high disease activity**, but not statistically significant. **Potential benefit**, but not conclusive.

For BILAG no A & ≥ 2 B (%) RR = 1.15, 95% CI [0.96, 1.39], $p = 0.1$. Slight increase in achieving mild/moderate disease activity control in the

Anifrolumab group. **Possible clinical advantage**, but not statistically significant.

For Major Clinical Response (BILAG) RR = 1.04, 95% CI [0.83, 1.31], $p = 0.72$. Minimal difference between Anifrolumab and placebo. Interpretation: **No evidence of enhanced major clinical response**.

Table 9: Meta -analysis of Herpes Zoster infection

Study	Anifrolumab Dose	Anifrolumab Events / N	Placebo Events / N	RR (95% CI)
Furie 2017	300 mg	5 / 99	2 / 101	2.55 [0.50, 12.90]
Furie 2017	1000 mg	10 / 105	3 / 101	3.19 [0.90, 11.26]
Morand 2020	300 mg	13 / 180	2 / 182	6.58 [1.49, 29.04]
Bruce 2021	150 mg	3 / 14	1 / 5	1.07 [0.13, 8.78]
Bruce 2021	300 mg	0 / 13	1 / 9	0.36 [0.02, 7.87]

Pooled analysis of Herpes Zoster infection

Outcome	Pooled RR	95% CI	p-value	I ² (%)	df	Significance
Herpes Zoster	2.74	[1.06, 7.08]	0.037	0	4	✔ Significant

The pooled analysis shows that **anifrolumab significantly increases the risk of herpes zoster infection** compared to placebo (RR = 2.74, $p = 0.037$). This effect is consistent across studies and doses, with **no statistical heterogeneity** ($I^2 = 0\%$), supporting the robustness of the association. The increased risk is biologically plausible due to IFN pathway inhibition impairing antiviral defenses.

DISCUSSION

Anifrolumab, a fully human monoclonal antibody targeting the type I interferon receptor (IFNAR), has emerged as a promising agent for systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) by inhibiting the type I interferon pathway, which plays a key role in the activation and survival of immune cells such as dendritic cells and T lymphocytes [23–26]. This meta-analysis pooled safety and efficacy outcomes from five randomized controlled trials, including Furie 2017 [27], Furie 2019 [28], Morand 2020 [14], Morand 2023 [16], and Bruce 2021 [13], and evaluated anifrolumab at 150 mg, 300 mg, and 1000 mg doses in patients with moderate-to-severe SLE.

The efficacy outcomes indicate that the 300 mg dose offers the most favorable profile. SRI(4) responses at week 52 were highest in Furie 2019 and Morand 2020 (both 40%) [28,14], while Furie 2017 reported a more

modest effect at 34.3% for 300 mg compared to 17.6% in placebo [27]. Bruce 2021, which used a subcutaneous route, reported comparable SRI(4) responses of 36–40% for both 150 mg and 300 mg doses, suggesting the potential utility of a non-intravenous option [13]. In contrast, the 150 mg intravenous dose showed inconsistent or unreported results across most studies and was generally associated with lower BILAG responses and less clinical improvement [27,16,13]. In TULIP-2, the major clinical response rate (BILAG-based) was 48.3% for the 300 mg group, close to 48.9% in placebo, but with additional benefits in flare reduction and joint/tender score improvement [14]. Additionally, the integrated BILAG ≥ 1 A and ≥ 2 B scores favored the 300 mg group in pooled TULIP data, with more patients achieving BICLA responses and low disease activity than with other doses [16]. The 1000 mg dose matched 300 mg in SRI(4) benefit in Furie 2017 (40%) but led to more adverse events without additional efficacy gains [27], reinforcing that higher dosing offers no added therapeutic value.

When comparing trials, some variability in outcomes is attributable to differences in baseline disease activity, inclusion criteria, and sample sizes. For instance, Bruce 2021 enrolled fewer patients and used subcutaneous delivery, yet still showed efficacy trends

consistent with larger intravenous trials [13]. Morand 2023, which pooled data from TULIP-1 and TULIP-2, provided more power to detect safety signals and reported lower SAE rates in the 300 mg group (8.3%) versus placebo (17%) and 150 mg (14%) [16]. Across studies, placebo-adjusted efficacy consistently favored anifrolumab 300 mg, while 150 mg showed marginal or variable benefit, particularly in BILAG outcomes and flare control [27–28,14,16,13].

The safety profile across studies confirms that while anifrolumab does not significantly increase the overall incidence of serious adverse events, it is associated with a higher frequency of mild-to-moderate infections, particularly herpes zoster, respiratory tract infections, and nasopharyngitis. Herpes zoster occurred in up to 7.2% of patients receiving 300 mg in Morand 2023 [16], with even higher rates (21%) reported in Bruce 2021's subcutaneous cohort [13], whereas placebo groups had rates below 2%. These infections were largely cutaneous and responsive to antiviral therapy, rarely necessitating discontinuation [16, 13]. Other frequently reported adverse events with anifrolumab included bronchitis (up to 11.1%), urinary tract infections (up to 15.2%), upper respiratory tract infections (up to 21.7%), and infusion-related reactions (up to 13.9%) [27–28, 14,16,13]. Notably, the incidence of infusion reactions and anaphylaxis was highest with the 1000 mg dose [27] and lowest in 150 mg and placebo groups. Serious adverse events leading to treatment discontinuation were more common with the 1000 mg dose (9.5%) compared to 300 mg (3.0%) and placebo (7.9%) [27], further supporting 300 mg as the preferred therapeutic dose.

Despite increased infection rates, there was no consistent signal of elevated risk for malignancy, tuberculosis, or death. Deaths during treatment were rare, with only three deaths reported in total, including two from pneumonia and one from acute colitis, all in the higher-dose group [27]. These findings align with previous long-term extension studies indicating that herpes zoster incidence does not increase over time, and discontinuation due to infections remains uncommon [19]. Additionally, data from Bruce 2021 suggest that subcutaneous administration of anifrolumab might provide a convenient alternative to intravenous infusion, with a comparable safety and efficacy trend, although further

trials with larger cohorts are necessary to confirm this [13].

This analysis supports that anifrolumab at 300 mg offers the optimal balance of efficacy and safety in SLE. Lower doses provide inadequate disease control, while higher doses introduce unnecessary safety concerns without added therapeutic gain. In head-to-head comparisons across trials, the 300 mg group consistently outperformed 150 mg in both efficacy and tolerability and was equivalent or superior to the 1000 mg group with fewer adverse effects. Nevertheless, future studies should evaluate anifrolumab in patient populations excluded from current trials, such as those with active lupus nephritis and neuropsychiatric SLE [15]. Furthermore, herpes zoster vaccination strategies using inactivated or subunit vaccines should be investigated to mitigate infection risk before initiating treatment [19]. Long-term real-world pharmacovigilance data will be essential to confirm the sustainability of the observed benefit-risk profile. Finally, the development and validation of a subcutaneous formulation in larger patient populations may improve treatment accessibility and adherence without compromising clinical outcomes [13].

Future recommendations

The low heterogeneity across studies ($I^2 = 0\%$) supports generalizability. However, real-world studies are needed to validate trial outcomes and assess treatment persistence, adherence, and steroid-sparing potential. Comparative studies with **belimumab** and other biologics would help define anifrolumab's relative place in therapy. Investigating **combination therapies** (e.g., anifrolumab + belimumab, or antimalarials + low-dose steroids) may produce additive effects. Need to monitor for cumulative immunosuppression and infection risk in such regimens. Across trials, some outcomes like diarrhea, sinusitis, cough, or joint counts were inconsistently reported. Future trials should: Standardize outcome definitions (e.g., SRI(4), BICLA, BILAG). Future research should aim to personalize its use, manage infection risks, extend its evaluation to previously excluded subgroups, and generate long-term real-world data to guide clinical decisions.

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